

Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention at a Glance:

Addressing Risky Substance Use among People with HIV

Substance use disorders can adversely affect all stages of care for people with HIV, including engaging in treatment and sustaining HIV viral suppression.¹ Therefore, addressing risky substance use among people with HIV is key to supporting the Ending the HIV Epidemic initiative in the United States.^{2,3} The Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention (MIBI) is a tool that effectively addresses problematic substance use among people with HIV and is feasible to implement.⁴ HIV service organizations (HSOs) and others that support people with HIV can integrate this intervention to better support those in need.

✦ MIBI Overview

The MIBI is a 15- to 30-minute brief intervention delivered privately either in person or remotely and delivered once or over multiple sessions, depending on the needs of the client. Using motivational interviewing (MI), a facilitator guides a client to explore their reasons for change within an atmosphere of acceptance and compassion and encourages them to progress along the stages of change by eliciting change talk (**Figure 1**).⁵

Figure 1. The MI Hill and Stages of Change

This includes leveraging four overlapping tasks that build upon one another over the course of the conversation: Engage, Focus, Evoke, and Plan (**Figure 2**). The MIBI further involves following up with referrals to substance use treatment and community supports as needed.⁵

Figure 2. The Four Tasks of MI for Substance Use
(Adapted from MIBI Manual)

◆ Does the MIBI Work?

MI is considered effective for addressing problematic use of alcohol, marijuana, and other drugs (e.g., cocaine, heroin) and increasing engagement in treatment for substance use disorder.⁶⁻⁸ When assessing the fit of nine evidence-based treatments for substance use disorder for HSOs in the United States to implement, MI was identified as having the greatest promise.²

The MIBI has been tested in HSOs and has been established as an effective tool for reducing risky substance use among people with HIV.^{4,9,10} The brief nature of the MIBI makes it feasible for HSOs to integrate into client care.

◆ Components

- Screening to identify risky substance use
 - 15- to 30-minute MI-based conversation tailored to the client
 - Referral to appropriate services as needed and follow-up on change plan if developed
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◆ Staffing

The MIBI can be implemented by a range of service providers, including counselors, case managers, social workers, addiction specialists, nurses, and physicians, as long as they receive adequate training to provide it appropriately. Existing staff at HSOs can be trained to integrate the MIBI into care for clients.

◆ Resources

There are multiple resources available for providers and their supervisors to learn about MI broadly and the MIBI specifically.¹¹ Listed here are a sampling that may be especially helpful to those seeking to implement the MIBI for people with HIV and risky substance use.

Tour of MI. A free 4-hour, virtual self-paced training on MI that can provide continuing education certificates.

MIBI manual. A free 53-page manual that includes background on MI, an overview of the MIBI, and MIBI-specific scripts, materials, and handouts. Handouts include tools for MIBI conversations, such as a checklist to identify reasons for quitting or cutting back and a change plan contract. (See **Appendix A** for the full manual.)

Online practice tools. Tools leveraging artificial intelligence can provide interactive training and feedback. [Lyssn](#) provides feedback on real or practice MIBI session recordings to help providers improve facilitation skills, offering scores for empathy, active listening, affirmations, and more. [SIMmersion](#) offers virtual clients with who providers can role-play to practice delivering the MIBI.

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